
ENERGY-HUNGRY VS. ENERGY-EFFICIENT: A DATA STUDY ON HOW IOT DEVICES TALK TO THE WEB

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ABSTRACT

This research examines various issues related to the power usage of different types of Internet of Things (IoT) devices. Energy-hungry IoT devices typically transmit more data, use more inefficient means of transmitting that data, and as a result use more power and have a shorter lifespan than energy-efficient IoT devices. Energy-efficient IoT devices transmit data using optimised procedures. As a result, energy-efficient IoT devices transmit data at a far lower rate with less power use while maintaining the same performance.

Keywords: Energy, IOT, Web

INTRODUCTION

Regarding energy, a frequently found definition in common literature as well as in textbooks is “energy is the ability to do work” or slightly more detailed “energy is the capacity of a system to do work” [Atkins 1990]. This is the original historic meaning, however nowadays incomplete as it misses “the ability to supply heat”. And even for what is mentioned, the meaning of “work” and “ability” or “capacity” is not explained. Energy can be converted between the different energy forms, while overall energy is conserved. The conservation of energy is a fundamental concept in physics, like the conservation of mass and the conservation of momentum. (Mehling, 2017)

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To examine the communication patterns of IoT devices in terms of data transmission frequency, packet size, and protocol usage.
- To differentiate between energy-hungry and energy-efficient IoT devices based on their network behavior and power consumption.
- To analyze the impact of various communication protocols (such as HTTP, MQTT, CoAP) on energy consumption in IoT systems.
- To identify key factors contributing to high energy consumption in IoT devices.
- To study the relationship between network conditions and energy usage in IoT device communication.
- To provide recommendations for designing sustainable and energy-efficient IoT systems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY**The study relies on secondary data, collected from:**

- Research journals and published papers (IEEE, Springer, Elsevier)
- Industry reports (IoT analytics, energy consumption reports)
- Open datasets on IoT communication and power usage
- Technical documentation on IoT protocols (MQTT, HTTP, CoAP)

Data is collected through:

- Review of existing literature on IoT energy consumption
- Extraction of relevant datasets from online repositories
- Case studies of IoT devices (e.g., smart sensors, wearables, smart home devices)

IOT

The Internet of things refers to a type of network to connect anything with the Internet based on stipulated protocols through information sensing equipments to conduct information exchange and communications in order to achieve smart recognitions, positioning, tracing, monitoring, and administration. In this paper we briefly discussed about what IOT is, how IOT enables different technologies, about its architecture, characteristics & applications, IOT functional view & what are the future challenges for IOT. (K.K Patel, 2016)

Web:

The web is a system of interlinked, hypertext documents accessed via the Internet. With a web browser, a user views web pages that may contain text, images, videos, other multimedia and navigates between them using hyperlinks. The web was created in 1989 by Sir Tim Berners-Lee, working at CERN (The European Organization for Nuclear Research) in Geneva, Switzerland. Since then, Berners-Lee has played an active role in guiding the development of web standards (such as the markup languages in which web pages are composed), in recent years has advocated his vision of a Semantic web. (Naik, et. 2009)

Communication patterns of IoT devices

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a dynamic global information network consisting of Internet-connected objects, such as RFIDs, sensors, actuators, as well as other instruments and smart appliances that are becoming an integral component of the future Internet. Over the last decade, we have seen a large number of the IoT solutions developed by start-ups, small and medium enterprises, large corporations, academic research institutes (such as universities), and private and public research organizations making their way into the market. In this paper, we survey over 100 IoT smart solutions in the marketplace and examine them closely in order to identify their applications and the technologies they use. More importantly, we identify the trends, opportunities, and open challenges in the industry-based IoT solutions. Based on the application domain, we classify and discuss these solutions under five different categories: 1) smart wearable; 2) smart home; 3) smart city; 4) smart environment; and 5) smart enterprise. This survey is intended to serve as a guideline and a conceptual framework for future research in the IoT and to motivate and inspire further developments. It also provides a systematic exploration of existing research and suggests a number of potentially significant research directions. 14 INDEX TERMS Internet of Things, industry solutions, IoT marketplace.

Communication in IoT devices typically involves the wireless transmission of data between devices and a central server or between devices themselves in a network. The process of wireless communication—whether it's sending a simple sensor reading or receiving instructions from a control unit—requires significant energy, particularly because it often involves maintaining a wireless connection, processing data for transmission, and sometimes, encrypting that data for security purposes. (Chandrakar, Rajoo, 2024)

Energy-hungry and energy-efficient IoT devices

Energy-hungry IoT devices are generally those that require continuous data transmission (cameras), high-frequency processing (AI edge devices), or constant interaction with cloud services. These devices often use high-throughput connectivity protocols like Wi-Fi or LTE, which can consume significant power (50–200 mA) during operation.

Energy-efficient IoT devices prioritize low-power consumption through techniques like Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), deep sleep modes, and energy harvesting, extending battery life for months or years. Key examples include smart thermostats (Nest), wearable health trackers (Fitbit, Oura Ring), LoRaWAN environmental sensors, smart lighting systems, and energy-harvesting building sensors.

1. Some of the Energy hungry IOT devices are as follows:

- **Smart TVs:** Smart TVs are televisions with internet connectivity built into them, allowing viewers to stream content similar to a smartphone or a personal computer. For example, Samsung's SmartThings IoT Hub includes its S90C TV, which relies on the Smart TV Hub to deliver high-quality resolution and a host of AI features.
- **Smart Refrigerators:** A smart refrigerator is an internet-connected appliance that often comes equipped with a touchscreen, cameras and sensors, enabling users to control it remotely via their smartphone. Samsung has upgraded its smart fridges, supplementing IoT technology with AI features. (Kawamoto, 2025).
- **Continuous Glucose Monitors:** Continuous glucose monitors (CGMs) are devices worn on the body that track the wearer's glucose levels in real time. These systems often consist of a skin-applied sensor, a transmitter and a receiver, such as a smartphone. For example, Dexcom's G6 one-touch applicator inserts a small sensor just beneath your skin, which continuously measures your glucose level and sends the data wirelessly to a display device via a transmitter, according to the company's website.
- **Equipment Monitoring Systems:** Samsara is an IoT company building solutions that give organizations comprehensive data visibility to support safe, efficient and sustainable physical operations. For example, its equipment monitoring technology offers location tracking to combat losses from theft and utilization reporting that helps businesses understand how often each piece of machinery is used so they can optimize resource allocation. (Kawamoto, 2025).

2. Some of the Energy Efficient IOT devices are as follows:

- **Amazon Fire TV Stick:** With the latest Fire Stick model that includes 4K streaming with Alexa voice remote, the Amazon Fire TV Stick is a streaming solution that meets many other household needs. Whether a user is ordering more detergent through their Amazon Prime shopping cart or pulling up live home security feeds on the TV, the Alexa-enabled Fire Stick gives a user access to more than their favorite TV shows and movies. (Crockett, 2023)
- **Wearables:** Fitness trackers or smartwatches continuously monitor patients' vital signs, such as heart rate or blood sugar levels. The IoT devices automatically transmit the data to medical professionals, who recognize abnormalities at an early stage and intervene. (2026)
- **Intelligent lighting:** Lamps are automatically adjusted to the time of day or presence of people. (2026)
- **Smart Rings:** Oura Ring monitors activity/sleep with high efficiency, often preferred for battery longevity over smartwatches.

FINDINGS

Impact of various communication protocols on Energy Consumption in IOT Systems

Communication protocols assist varied network devices to converse with each other by transmitting the analog signals, digital signals, different files & process the data from one device to other devices. These types of protocols are applicable in telecommunication & computer networks where suitable rules are executed to transmit information from source to destination. The most vital protocols within networking are TCP (Transmission Control Protocol) & User datagram protocol (UDP).

Impacts are as follows:

- **Wireless Personal Area Network (WPAN)**

According to IoT Analytics' latest "State of the IoT & Short-term outlook" update, the majority of IoT devices are connected through **short-range technology: Wireless Personal Area Network (WPAN)** that does not exceed a maximum range of 100m. Devices include **Bluetooth**-connected headsets for example, but also **ZigBee** and **Z-wave** connected devices mostly used in home applications such as building control systems, smart alarms, or smart thermostats but also Industry 4.0 applications.

ZigBee and **6LoWPAN** protocols are designed for low power consumption applications such as low power wireless sensor networks. However, the transmission time for those protocols is longer than the low power Wi-Fi, due to its low data rate (250 Kb/s). **The average consumption profile is therefore considered as low to medium depending on the application and the module used.** (SAFT, 2020)

- **Wireless Local Area Networks (WLAN)**

Next up is **Wireless Local Area Networks**, a network that enables connectivity of up to 1 kilometer. In this category, **Wi-Fi** is the most common standard. The technology is supporting devices such as home assistants, smart TVs, and smart speakers and is sometimes used in industrial settings like factories. Wi-Fi was historically designed for laptops or PCs, where the power requirements were not so important. **It was deemed too power hungry for battery-powered smart objects which led manufacturers to develop new standards for the Internet of Things.** New generation, **low power Wi-Fi** operates at much higher data rates ranging from 1 Mb/s to 54 Mb/s. This allows Wi-Fi enabled sensors to spend very little time with actual transmission or reception. The chips 'sleep mode' power consumption was also greatly reduced (convenient for IoT applications since these devices are mostly in the sleep state) thus **reducing the modules overall power consumption.**

- **Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN)**

IoT applications' requirements have driven the emergence of Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN) and we can expect a massive growth in the number of IoT devices connected through them. According to McKinsey, 100 percent of the population should have LPWAN coverage by 2022 and by 2025, it is expected that more than 2 billion devices will be connected through LPWAN.

The technology offers low power, long range (up to 10–50 km in rural zones and 1–10 km in urban zones) together with low-cost specifications. Four main competing standards are currently sharing the market: **Sigfox**, **LoRaWAN**, **LTE-M** and **NB-IoT**. They are presently being rolled-out worldwide with more than 25 million devices already connected, the majority of which are smart meters. These protocols may be based on cellular technology, such as LTE-M and NB-IoT or radio-based (LoRa, Sigfox), they can be licensed (NB-IoT, LTE-M) or unlicensed (LoRa, Sigfox) which also differentiates their availability and prices.

In long range connectivity, LoRaWAN requires more transmission time compared to small range connectivity protocols because of its low rate data rate. However, the optimizations brought to power savings mode, small data maximization, and flexible sleep **all reduce the power**. (SAFT, 2020)

- **Cellular technology (2G, 3G, 4G and 5G)**

Before the advent of LPWAN, cellular technology (2G, 3G, and 4G) was the only option for long-range remote device connectivity (up to 100km). The new, much talked about, 5G technology that is currently being deployed, promises a massive bandwidth and extremely low latency which could favor its adoption. Cellular connectivity has historically been focused on range and bandwidth at the expense of power consumption. The high amount of data produced by devices was hard to process quickly and the amount of time between when data is sent from a connected device to when it returns to the same device—the latency—was high. However, **new cellular technologies like 5G transmit data about 10 times faster than 4G, promising ultra-low latency and lower power consumption.**

- **Wireless Neighborhood Area Networks (WNAN)**

Finally, somewhere in between WLAN and long-range technologies, lies **Wireless Neighborhood Area Networks (WNAN)**, a medium range technology that covers areas between 5-10 km with its typical proponents, **Mesh networks (Wi-Sun (6LoWPAN), JupiterMesh or ZigBee-NAN)**. The technology can be used as an alternative for LPWA/Cellular (e.g. in Utilities Field Area Networks) or as a complimentary element (e.g., for remote metering where other protocols do not have sufficient range to be implemented) such as gas metering applications).

WNAN networks are generally deemed as high-energy consumers but mesh technologies such as Wi-SUN can provide high data rates and low latency. Additionally, **Wi-SUN modules use less power for listening which enable customers to configure devices to listen frequently and still maintain a long-life.** (SAFT, 2020)

The relationship between network conditions and energy usage in IoT device communication:

Network conditions directly dictate IoT device energy consumption: poor signal strength, high latency, or congested networks increase transmission times and packet retransmissions, leading to significantly higher energy drain. Conversely, stable, high-bandwidth connections allow rapid data transfer and longer sleep modes, optimizing battery life for battery-operated devices.

Key relationships between network conditions and IoT energy usage include:

- **Signal Strength and Re-transmissions:** Poor network conditions result in low signal-to-noise ratios, causing data loss. The device must re-transmit data, which is one of the most energy-intensive activities for IoT sensors, quickly depleting batteries.
- **Transmission Time & Latency:** In low-speed or high-latency environments, IoT devices must keep their radio components active longer to transmit or receive data (including acknowledgments/ACKs). This increased "listening" time or active time consumes more energy, whereas faster protocols/networks allow devices to enter low-power sleep states sooner.
- **Protocol Overhead:** The choice of protocol (e.g., HTTP vs. MQTT) significantly affects energy usage under specific network conditions. Larger protocol headers require longer transmission times, increasing energy consumption per packet.
- **Network Congestion and Retries:** High network congestion increases the chance of packet collisions. Devices may need to implement back-off algorithms and re-transmit, consuming extra power.
- **Edge Computing Impact:** Under poor or unreliable network conditions, processing data closer to the source (edge computing) is used to avoid sending vast amounts of data over a weak network, thus saving energy.

Strategies to mitigate energy issues due to poor network conditions include implementing adaptive transmission power control, utilizing energy-efficient protocols like MQTT or CoAP, and optimizing data transmission intervals.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the energy consumption of IoT devices is highly dependent on their communication patterns, protocol selection, and network conditions. Energy-hungry IoT devices, such as smart TVs and continuous monitoring systems, consume significant power due to continuous data transmission, high processing requirements, and reliance on high-bandwidth communication technologies like Wi-Fi and cellular

networks. In contrast, energy-efficient devices adopt optimized strategies such as low-power protocols, reduced transmission frequency, and sleep modes, which significantly extend battery life without affecting functionality.

The analysis further reveals that communication protocols play a crucial role in determining energy efficiency. Lightweight protocols such as MQTT and CoAP are more suitable for low-power IoT environments compared to HTTP due to lower data overhead and faster transmission. Additionally, network conditions such as signal strength, latency, and congestion directly impact energy usage, where poor conditions lead to retransmissions and increased power consumption.

Overall, the study highlights that efficient IoT system design requires a balance between performance and energy consumption, achieved through appropriate protocol selection, optimized communication patterns, and adaptive strategies based on network conditions.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the study, the following suggestions are recommended:

1. Adoption of Lightweight Protocols

IoT systems should prioritize the use of energy-efficient communication protocols such as MQTT and CoAP instead of HTTP to reduce transmission overhead and power consumption.

2. Optimization of Data Transmission

Devices should implement data aggregation and adaptive transmission scheduling to minimize unnecessary communication and conserve energy.

3. Use of Low-Power Communication Technologies

Technologies such as Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), ZigBee, and LoRaWAN should be encouraged for applications requiring long battery life.

4. Efficient Network Management

Improving network conditions by reducing congestion and ensuring stable connectivity can significantly lower energy consumption caused by retransmissions and delays.

5. Implementation of Sleep Modes

IoT devices should incorporate deep sleep or idle modes to reduce energy usage during inactive periods.

6. Integration of Edge Computing

Processing data locally at the device level can reduce the need for continuous data transmission to cloud servers, thereby saving energy.

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